

Supplementary Materials: Tables

Table 1

Excerpts used in the instrument identification task indicated by their starting measure, their type and duration. Mixture instruments by voice with their abbreviation, part number (if applicable), and F0-register.

Excerpt	Type	Voice 1			Voice 2			Voice 3			Voice 4			Duration
M2	chord	ob	2	high	eh	–	mid	bn	1	high	cl	2	low	2.9 s
M6	chord	cl	1	high	eh	–	mid	ob	2	low	bn	2	mid	2.9 s
M10	chord	cl	1	high	eh	–	mid	ob	2	low	hn	2	mid	2.6 s
M12	chord	fl	1	high	ob	1	high	cl	1	high	eh	–	mid	2.6 s
M16	non-chord	ob	1	mid	vn	2	mid	cl	1	low	hn	4	low	3.4 s
M34	non-chord	ob	1	mid	vn	2	mid	hn	1	mid	bn	1	high	2.4 s
M35	non-chord	cl	2	mid	bn	2	high	eh	–	mid	hn	2	low	3.1 s
M41	non-chord	fl	1	high	cl	1	high	eh	–	mid	hn	3	mid	3.0 s
M45	non-chord	vn	2	mid	eh	–	mid	bn	1	high	hn	1	mid	2.2 s
M56	non-chord	vn	2	mid	bn	1	high	vc	–	high	hn	3	mid	2.9 s
M72	non-chord	fl	2	mid	vc	–	high	bn	2	high	hn	4	mid	2.4 s
M74	non-chord	fl	1	mid	hn	1	mid	bn	2	high	vc	–	mid	2.3 s

Table 2

Excerpts with full orchestration used in the sound quality rating task. Excerpts are indicated by their starting measure. Range of measures, dynamic level, duration, and orchestration.

Ex.	Meas.	Dyn.	Dur.	Orchestration
M1	1–3	<i>p</i>	14.7 s	2ob, eh, 2cl, 2bn, vc
M15	15–17	<i>f</i>	12.3 s	2fl, 2ob, eh, 2cl, 3bn, 4hn, strings
M17	17–19	<i>f</i>	13.5 s	bcl, 3bn, va, vc, db
M33	33–36	<i>mf</i>	16.0 s	ob, eh, 2cl, bcl, 3bn, 4hn, strings (-vn1)
M42	42–44	<i>f</i>	11.5 s	3bn, strings
M61	61–63	<i>f</i>	11.3 s	3fl, 2ob, eh, 2cl, bcl, 3bn, 4hn, strings
M73	73–75	<i>ff</i>	10.3 s	3fl, 2ob, eh, 2cl, bcl, 3bn, 4hn, 3tbn, tba, timp, strings
M82	82–84	<i>ff</i>	9.5 s	3fl, 2ob, eh, 2cl, bcl, 3bn, 4hn, 2tpt, 3tbn, tba, timp, strings
M94	94–96	<i>f</i>	13.1 s	ob, eh, 2bn, 2hn, vn2, vc, db
M96	96–98	<i>p</i>	12.4 s	2ob, eh, bcl, 2bn, strings

Table 3

Mean identification accuracy per excerpt and instrument.

Excerpt	Mean instrument accuracy	Instruments (abbreviation)								
		fl	ob	eh	cl	bn	hn	vn	vc	
M2	0.35	–	0.39	0.32	0.31	0.38	–	–	–	
M6	0.36	–	0.08	0.44	0.32	0.61	–	–	–	
M10	0.27	–	0.29	0.36	0.11	–	0.32	–	–	
M12	0.36	0.83	0.21	0.23	0.17	–	–	–	–	
M16	0.36	–	0.24	–	0.42	–	0.06	0.73	–	
M34	0.30	–	0.02	–	–	0.31	0.62	0.24	–	
M35	0.32	–	–	0.23	0.42	0.51	0.14	0	–	
M41	0.46	0.91	–	0.27	0.19	–	0.46	–	–	
M45	0.34	–	–	0.37	–	0.13	0.01	0.86	–	
M56	0.42	–	–	–	–	0.12	0.60	0.55	0.43	
M72	0.33	0.08	–	–	–	0.19	0.79	–	0.25	
M74	0.43	0.49	–	–	–	0.24	0.25	–	0.73	
mean	0.36	0.58	0.21	0.32	0.28	0.31	0.36	0.59	0.47	

Generalized binomial mixed-effects model statistics (instrument identification)**Table 4:** Instrument model: GLMM results for instruments as fixed effects and their individual estimate (β), low and high confidence interval (CI), z-value, and p-value.

Predictor	β	CI low	CI high	z-value	p-value
Intercept	-0.49	-0.77	-0.21	-3.56	< .001
Flute	0.85	0.62	1.08	7.25	< .001
Oboe	-1.05	-1.27	-0.83	-9.24	< .001
English horn	-0.50	-0.69	-0.32	-5.23	< .001
Clarinet	-0.74	-0.94	-0.55	-7.47	< .001
Bassoon	-0.30	-0.47	-0.13	-3.41	< .001
French horn	0.01	-0.15	0.16	0.08	.935
Violins	1.10	0.86	1.33	9.12	< .001
Cellos	0.64	0.37	0.90	4.66	< .001

Table 5: Acoustic condition model: GLMM results for reverberation (off/on), spatial distribution (center/spread), and their interaction as fixed effects.

Predictor	β	CI low	CI high	z-value	p-value
Intercept	-0.49	-1.12	0.14	-1.69	.092
reverb	-0.03	-0.10	0.04	-0.78	.435
spatialDist	-0.04	-0.11	0.02	-1.28	.202
reverb:spatialDist	0.06	-0.01	0.13	1.77	.078

Table 6: Training effect model: GLMM results for trial number, reverberation (off/on), spatial distribution (center/spread), and their interaction as fixed effects.

Predictor	β	CI low	CI high	z-value	p-value
Intercept	-0.50	-1.15	0.16	-1.66	.096
trialNum	0.17	0.10	0.25	4.69	< .001
reverb	-0.04	-0.11	0.03	-1.19	.235
spatialDist	-0.02	-0.09	0.04	-0.71	.480
trialNum:reverb	-0.01	-0.08	0.06	-0.24	.814
trialNum:spatialDist	-0.07	-0.14	0.00	-1.89	.058
reverb:spatialDist	0.06	-0.01	0.13	1.67	.096
trialNum:reverb:spatialDist	-0.15	-0.22	-0.07	-4.02	< .001

Table 7: Voice (categorical) model: GLMM results for voice (categorical; 1-highest to 4-lowest) as categorical fixed effect.

Predictor	β	CI low	CI high	<i>z</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value
Intercept	-0.51	-1.13	0.10	-1.80	0.072
voice1	0.33	0.14	0.53	3.34	< .001
voice2	-0.21	-0.34	-0.08	-3.09	.002
voice3	-0.13	-0.27	0.00	-1.89	.058
voice4	0.01	-0.16	0.17	0.09	.929

Table 8: Voice (numerical) model: GLMM results for voice (numerical; linear, quadratic) as fixed effect.

Predictor	β	CI low	CI high	<i>z</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value
Intercept	0.50	-0.27	1.26	1.30	.193
voice	-0.90	-1.35	-0.45	-3.96	< .001
voice2	0.17	0.08	0.25	3.89	< .001

Table 9: Register model: GLMM results for register (categorical; low, middle, high) as fixed effects.

Predictor	β	CI low	CI high	<i>z</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value
Intercept	-0.72	-1.34	-0.11	-2.51	.012
low	-0.49	-0.67	-0.30	-5.20	< .001
middle	0.61	0.45	0.77	7.48	< .001
high	-0.12	-0.29	0.05	-1.41	.159

Table 10: Pitch model: GLMM results for pitch (F0) (numerical; linear, quadratic, and interaction terms) as fixed effect.

Predictor	β	CI low	CI high	<i>z</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value
Intercept	-0.77	-1.42	-0.13	-2.54	.011
F0	-0.39	-0.59	-0.19	-3.82	< .001
F02	0.12	0.03	0.21	2.61	.009
F0:F2	0.28	0.23	0.34	10.66	< .001

Table 11: Register and pitch model: Combined GLMM results for pitch (F0) and register as fixed effects.

Predictor	β	CI low	CI high	<i>z</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value
Intercept	-0.99	-1.70	-0.28	-2.96	.003
low	-0.07	-0.37	0.24	-0.42	0.67
middle	0.60	0.42	0.78	6.45	< .001
high	-0.53	-0.79	-0.28	-4.10	< .001
F0	-0.27	-0.53	-0.00	-1.99	.046
F02	0.18	0.08	0.27	3.63	< .001
F0:F02	0.29	0.24	0.34	10.90	< .001

Table 12: Average (mix) acoustic similarity model: GLMM results for average spectral centroid (SC) height, spectral flux (SF) correlation, and Mel-frequency cepstral coefficient (MFCC) correlation as fixed effects.

Predictor	β	CI low	CI high	<i>z</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value
Intercept	-0.60	-1.48	0.27	-1.43	.152
avg_sc_mix	0.86	0.61	1.11	6.65	< .001
corr_sf_mix	-0.76	-0.97	-0.55	-7.16	< .001
corr_mfcc_mix	-0.21	-0.38	-0.05	-2.54	.011

Table 13: Single acoustic similarity model: GLMM results for average SC height, SF correlation, and MFCC correlation as fixed effects.

Predictor	β	CI low	CI high	<i>z</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value
Intercept	-0.63	-1.35	0.10	-1.79	.074
avg_sc_single	0.67	0.46	0.88	6.33	< .001
corr_sf_single	-0.74	-0.97	-0.53	-6.68	< .001
corr_mfcc_single	-0.31	-0.45	-0.17	-4.34	< .001

Linear mixed-effects model statistics (sound quality ratings)**Table 14:** Transparency model: LMM results for reverberation (on/off), spatial distribution (spread/center), and their interaction as fixed effects.

Predictor	β	CI low	CI high	t -value	p -value
Intercept	4.68	4.33	5.02	26.89	< .001
Reverb	0.21	0.11	0.31	4.17	< .001
spatialDist	0.35	0.25	0.45	6.78	< .001
reverb:spatialDist	-0.16	-0.26	-0.06	-3.07	.002

Table 15: Sonority model: LMM results with the same fixed effects as in Table 11.

Predictor	β	CI low	CI high	t -value	p -value
Intercept	4.94	4.40	5.48	18.49	< .001
reverb	0.32	0.24	0.41	7.47	< .001
spatialDist	0.37	0.29	0.46	8.57	< .001
reverb:spatialDist	-0.17	-0.26	-0.09	-3.93	< .001

Table 16: Spatiality model: LMM results with the same fixed effects as in Table 11.

Predictor	β	CI low	CI high	t -value	p -value
Intercept	4.64	4.29	5.00	26.27	< .001
reverb	0.30	0.20	0.40	5.93	< .001
spatialDist	0.73	0.63	0.83	14.48	< .001
reverb:spatialDist	-0.19	-0.29	-0.09	-3.77	< .001

Table 17: Concert hall model: LMM results with the same fixed effects as in Table 11.

Predictor	β	CI low	CI high	t -value	p -value
Intercept	4.37	3.98	4.76	22.52	< .001
reverb	0.30	0.20	0.40	5.80	< .001
spatialDist	0.62	0.52	0.73	11.93	< .001
reverb:spatialDist	-0.22	-0.32	0.11	-4.15	< .001

Table 18: Overall rating model: LMM results with the same fixed effects as in Table 11.

Predictor	β	CI low	CI high	t -value	p -value
Intercept	4.57	4.25	4.89	28.94	< .001
reverb	0.42	0.12	0.30	9.22	< .001
spatialDist	0.21	0.33	0.51	4.69	< .001
reverb:spatialDist	-0.19	-0.28	-0.10	-4.15	< .001

Supplementary Materials: Figures

Figure 1: Sound quality ratings across acoustic condition for the rating scales transparency and concert hall, with binned individual participant ratings and bootstrapped 95% confidence intervals as error bars.

Figure 2: Mean sound quality ratings (across acoustic condition) for each rating scale in each excerpt.

Figure 3: Mean identification accuracy over average Gold-MSI scores for each participant.

